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STRATEGIC PLANNING AND ORGANIZATIONAL PERFORMANCE OF INSURANCE FIRMS IN RIVERS STATE.

Abstract

The purpose of this study was to explore the relationship between strategic planning and organizational performance of insurance firms in Rivers State. The objectives of the study were to ascertain how dimensions of strategic planning such as goal setting and mission and vision relate to organizational performance of insurance firms in Rivers State. A cross-sectional survey was used. The population of the study consisted of fifteen (15) insurance firms in Rivers State, Nigeria. The sample size comprised of sixty (60) respondents who were key managers selected from 4 different departments of insurance firms in Rivers State. Spearman Rank Order Correlation Coefficient was used for test of hypotheses. The findings revealed that strategic planning dimensions (goal setting and mission and vision) have a significant relationship with organizational performance of insurance firms in Rivers State. The study concluded that strategic planning influences organizational performance of insurance firms in Rivers State. The study recommended that; Insurance firm's managers should engage in more strategic planning practices through goal setting technique in order to realize consistent improvement in performance; the management should also involve all the stakeholders (top, middle and low level managers) when developing its mission and vision so that the mission statements can easily be understood by every person in the organization as this will make it easier to implement the strategic plan drawn

Keywords: *Strategic Planning, Goal Setting, Mission and Vision, Organizational Performance*

INTRODUCTION

The success of an organization will to a large extent depend on how well its strategists consider, address and outline proper approaches that will lead to solutions of the above strategic business questions. Strategic Planning assumes that an organization must be responsive to a dynamic and ever changing environment (Olang'o & Namusonge, 2018). Claudio (1999) argues that strategic planning practice is a game plan that sets specific goals and objectives but unlike a game plan, it is capable of being changed in response to shifting market dynamics (Olang'o & Namusonge, 2018). Organizational performance is about creating values for the primary beneficiaries of the organization. Efficient and effective strategic planning can increase profitability of Organization in terms of more sales and profit growth. Practicing the strategic planning in any business will show better performance compared with non-planning system (Wun, 2019).

Strategic planning as a process helps organizations in making better strategies through the use of more systematic, logical, and rational approach to strategic choice and brings about understanding and commitment from all managers and employees (Thompson, 2007; (Olang'o & Namusonge, 2018). When managers and employees understand what the organization does and why, they often feel a part of the organization and become committed to assisting it. The commitment usually makes the managers and employees surprisingly creative and innovative towards the achievement of the organizational goals and objectives. Besides helping firms avoid financial demise, strategic planning offers other tangible benefits, such as enhanced awareness of both external and internal threats, an improved understanding of competitors' strategies, increased employee productivity, reduced resistance to change, and clearer understanding of performance-reward relationships. With a strategic approach the managers and employees of a firm will be in a position to view change as an opportunity rather than a threat (Greenley, 2020).

Strategic planning is an approach used by managements of organizations and it involves a set of decisions and actions established by managers of the organization to provide organizational long-term direction, set specific performance objectives, develop strategies to achieve these objectives in the light of all the prevailing internal and external circumstances, and undertake to execute, monitor and control the chosen plans (Pierce & Robinson, 2007). It is a management technique intended to identify the strengths and weaknesses of the organizations, the challenges and opportunities facing it, and its vision of the future and how it will seek to achieve that vision. Harrison (2017) emphasizes that strategic planning and decision making is one of the most important aspects any manager will undertake in business. Strategic planning focuses on the organization's long term goals, assesses its capabilities to achieve those goals, examines environmental factors that may affect the organization, and identifies strategies designed to move the organization forward (Olang'o & Namusonge, 2018).

Strategic planning helps the organizations by first outlining the future organizational position or dream (vision) then defines the purpose of the organization (mission) and establishes realistic goals, objectives and detailed schedules (plans) consistent with the mission in a defined time frame within the institution's capacity for implementation (Olang'o & Namusonge, 2018). It communicates those goals, objectives and plans to the institutions' constituents and develops a sense of ownership of the plans, ensures that the most effective use is made of the available

organization's resources by focusing the resources on the key priorities. It also provides a base from which progress can be measured and establishes a mechanism for informed change when needed, brings together everyone's best and most reasoned efforts, have important value in building a consensus about where the institution is headed for today and in future (Olang'o & Namusonge, 2018).

More so, Past and recent research studies have made it clear that there is an increased internal and external uncertainty due to emerging opportunities and threats, lack of the awareness of needs and of the facilities related issues and environment and lack of direction.

Furthermore, many organizations spend most of their time realizing and reacting to unexpected changes and problems instead of anticipating and preparing for them. This is called crisis management organizations caught off guard may spend a great deal of time and energy playing catch up. They use up their energy coping with immediate problems with little energy left to anticipate and prepare for the next challenges. This vicious cycle locks many organizations into a reactive posture. This research study is to assess the effect of strategic planning on organizational performance, which at the long run enhances organizational profitability.

Strategic Plan provides the basic direction and rationale for determining the focus of an organization; and also provides the specification against which any organization may best decide what to do and how to do it. Simply put, it is a process for creating and describing a better future in measurable terms and the selection of the best means to achieve the results desired. It is important to note that not all planning is actually strategic even though they may be termed so. It is said that failure to plan leads to planning to fail.

Strategic planning process begins with the development of a vision that guides the formulation of organizational strategies (Haden, 2010). Effective strategic planning provides a framework for decision making on resource allocation, addressing organizational problems and achieving competitiveness by taking advantage of opportunities.

Statement of Problem

Some organizations disagree on the benefits of strategic planning processes and tools in today's volatile business environment; and results of strategic planning and performance linkage studies have been mixed. Those inconsistencies in both theoretical perspective and research results may

contribute to lack of planning due to difficulty in determining strategic planning benefits in general, and in knowing when or how approaches to planning need to be modified. These problems pose a lack of confidence on strategic planning activity which eventually results in organizations underperforming.

Conceptual Framework

Figure: 1.1 Fig 1.1: Conceptual Framework Showing the Relationship between Strategic Planning and Organisational Performance

Source: Samwel, (2018), Researcher's Adaptation (2023).

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The aim of the study was to examine the relationship between planning and organisational performance of insurance firms in Rivers State. . The specific objectives of the study were to:

1. Determine the relationship between goal setting and organisational performance of insurance firms in Rivers State
2. Examine the relationship between mission and vision and organisational performance of insurance firms in Rivers State.

Hypotheses

H01: There is no significant relationship between goal setting and organisational performance of insurance firms in Rivers State

H02: There is no significant relationship between mission and vision and organisational performance of insurance firms in Rivers State

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

The Concept of Strategic Planning

Strategic Planning obtains its basis from the concept that the future of an organization can be potentially influenced by actions undertaken in the present. The process involving the definition of the ideal future state of the organization, the formulation of a roadmap outlining how to achieve it and moving from the current state towards the organization's vision defines strategic planning. Steiner (2010) observes strategic planning as comprising of the setting of organizational goals, developing policies and strategies towards achieving these goals and the establishment of an in depth plan aimed at detailing the implementation process. With emphasis on prioritization and a focus on long term objectives, resources are allocated to ensure an alignment with the organization's vision (Marksberry, 2012).

Strategic planning is an approach used by management of organizations that involves a set of decisions and actions established by managers of the organization to provide organizational long-term direction, set specific performance objectives, develop sets of activities to be carried out, in a given time frame, to achieve these objectives in light of all the relevant internal and external circumstances, and undertake to execute, monitor and control the chosen plans (Pierce et al., 2007). It is a disciplined effort to produce fundamental decisions and actions that shape and guide what an organization is, what it does and why it does it (Bryson (2004). It plays a crucial role in explaining how organizations both private and public put policies into practice and define clear objectives (Bebbington, 2007).

Steiner (2010) defines Strategic Planning as a process whose aim is to outline strategy, set policies and develop detailed plans seeking to achieve organizational objectives. The deliberate effort by an organization's Management to integrate its strategy with the allocation of roles, responsibilities and resources in the actualization of the desired ideal future forms the backbone

of strategic

planning. The three key components of Strategic Planning include strategic analysis, strategic choice and strategic implementation. The formalization of logistics, operations and financial domains by both Management and industrial sciences has resulted in the complimenting of the quantitative arm with the qualitative human aspect of sociology, psychology, and human resource management. It is the combined quantitative and qualitative aspects that address different organization requirements including professional, financial, technical, and strategic needs.

Strategic planning focuses on defining the organizational direction, setting priorities, identifying the obstacles to organizational success and opportunities that can increase organizational competitiveness and performance. The planning process in organizations enhances sustainability through competitive strategies and requires utilization of information within the organization and externally.

Dimensions of Strategic

Planning Goals Setting

Goals are the broad, long-term accomplishments that an organization wants to attain, achieve or where it wants to be. They provide the overall context for what the vision tries to achieve (Nickels et al., 2020). They are powerful tools that break the vision statement into specific tasks and actions to attain desired results across the organization. They function as the yardstick for tracking an organization's performance or progress (Thompson et al, 2004). They must be measurable and time specific as against having vague objectives like „maximize profit“, „reduce costs“, become more efficient or „increase sales“.

The benefits of goal setting have been highlighted by various researchers (Draft, 2016; Goerg, 2015; TeamFME, 2013) who agree that goal setting help define the purpose for which organizations are established; as such it leads to increased productivity, ensures clarity in decision making, provides motivation, activate planning, grows organizations, encourage thought, has an energizing and a persistence effect on those for whom the goals are set, and helps to control the future direction or activities of an organization. From the aforementioned, some of the advantages of goal setting are that it provides a reference point against which workers can measure their satisfaction by dividing outcomes into gains, when the goal is attained, and losses, when output falls below the goal (George, 2015). Further, goal setting helps in the development of strategies

that supports performance to the required goal level, (Lunenburg, 2011; George, 2015; Draft, 2016). Despite these advantages, however, the limitation in the goal setting process still comes to light; this is mostly from the implementation process of set goals. Too difficult or complex goals can result in reduced cooperation among workers, increased risk taking, and may encourage unethical behavior such as cheating and misreporting in order to be seen as meeting up with the goal (George, 2015; Latham, 2006). Similarly, lowered output quality can also be the result of much emphasis on quantity which is a more measurable aspect of work (Opensax, 2019). Equally, very difficult and complex goals stimulate riskier behavior, to help address this limitation, the skills of those for which goals are set should be taken into account when setting goals. This calls for caution to be exercised in the application of goals, as too high emphasis on quantity which is a more measurable aspect of goal setting could lead to low quality and viceversa (Opensax, 2019).

The acronym SMART has been used to describe the basic features of goal setting, such that goals should be specific, measurable, attainable, relevant and time bound (TeamFME, 2013; George, 2015; Hoek, Groeneveld & Kuipers, 2018). Goal specificity implies that a well-defined goal should be in a unit form of measure that can be easily and clearly related with such as value, quantity of output, and weight, colour, size, and so on for quality, as opposed to a simple do your best rule. Measurable refers to the ability to observe progress so that an individual or observer knows how close goal attainment is. A goal should be attainable, which means that an individual has a realistic chance of achieving the goal. In addition, a goal need to be relevant, that means it should be meaningful and worth achieving for the individual or the organization, while timed goals implies that there should be some time limit or timeframe for reaching or completing the goal. Further studies on goal setting reveals that goal setting has four outcomes (Obasan & Sotunde, 2011) which include choice, effort, persistence and cognition.

The process of formulating corporate strategy involves; Developing a business mission, vision and establishing long term objectives. Identifying external opportunities and threat (external analysis), determining internal strengths and weaknesses (internal analysis), generating (crafting) alternative strategies (strategic options) and evaluating the alternatives and choosing particular strategies to pursue (pre-implementation evaluation).

Strategy formulation is the development of long-range plans for effective management of opportunities and threats in light of corporate strengths and weaknesses. It includes defining

corporate mission, specifying achievable objectives, developing strategies and setting policy guidelines (Stevenson, 2012). Corporate mission refers to the purpose for the organization's existence. It tells what the company is providing to the society, objectives tell what is to be accomplished, strategies state how the mission and objectives will be achieved, and policy serves as a broad guideline for decision making that links the formulation of a strategy with its implementation.

Mission and Vision

Mission and vision Bartkus, Glassman, and McAfee (2016) concludes that, mission and vision statements have a potential for influencing the organization's performance. Ireland and Hitt, (2013) asserts that organizations do this by examining the changes that have already taken place. Subsequently, there is near certainty that a global economy is imminent and that its beginning had an impact on leadership practices today. Effective strategic leadership may prove to be one of the most critical ways for an organization to achieve superior or even satisfactory performance when confronting challenges of the global economy. Researchers agree therefore that university management need to define a strategic mission and vision statement which will have a transformative effect on the future of the institution. Achua and Lussier (2016) defines organization mission statement as an enduring statement of purpose that distinguishes one organization from the other similar enterprises. It describes the business the organization pursues, and it is well explained and designed to provide many benefits to an organization, including providing direction and focus, forming the basis for objectives and strategies, inspiring positive emotions about the organization, ensuring unanimity of purpose, and helping resolve divergent views among managers (Yazhou, & Jian, 2011).

Ireland et al., (2016) asserts that a good mission statement should focus on the needs that the organization's products/services are meeting. It specifies the business in which the organization intends to compete and the customers it intends to serve (customer segment). The mission statement should be broad but distinguishes the organization from the others. It should be specific but not to the extent of being rigid and difficult to operationalize. Palmer and Short (2018) noted that business schools use mission statements to present their values, motivate faculty, recruit students, and promote their accreditation aspirations. Crafting a compelling mission statement is expensive consuming relatively large quantities of institutional resources. The chances of crafting

an effective mission increases when employees possess a strong focus of ethical standards that guide their behaviors as they strive to help the firm achieve its vision (Davis, Ruhe, Lee & Rajadhyasha, 2007). Any organization without a proactive mission and vision is doomed in the light of competitive environment. Universities need very specific mission and vision statements which reflect the aspirations of their leaders aimed at achieving the objectives and goals as guided by the regulators.

Kantabutra and Avery (2010) argues that vision on the other hand is an ambitious view of the future that everyone within the organization can believe in and that is not readily attainable yet offers a better future than what now exists. That a good vision facilitates growth in an organization will make sense to the organization's citizens and expand their minds in terms of possibilities while at the same time remaining feasible. Stid and Bradach, (2009) concludes that a clear vision determines very critical functions such as; enhancing decision making which facilitates people to determine what is important or trivial, appealing to followers on the fundamental needs, linking and rationalizing ways of doing things, proving meaning to work and establishing a standard of excellence. Ireland, et al., (2015) affirms that strategic leaders are people located in different areas and levels of the firm using strategic management process to select strategic actions that help the firm to achieve its vision and fulfill its mission. This kind of vision creates cohesion among members of the organization (Ireland, et.al. 2016). This makes organizations to meet their set objectives.

Organizational Performance

Organizational performance is the actual output of an organization measured against the expected outputs. Richard (2009) defines organizational performance as a summary of three key identifiable, measurable and specific outcome areas namely; Financial Performance, Shareholder Return, and Product Performance. Financial Performance is measurable in profits, return on investments and return on assets. Shareholder Return is measurable in total shareholder return, as well as a measure of economic value addition. Product Performance, on the other hand, can be measured in sales or market share achieved, new market penetration and customer feedback evaluation.

Strategic Planning and Organizational Performance

It is conceptualized that firms that have effectively embraced strategic planning, record better performance compared to those that have not. David (1997) argues that firms' record improved performance once they effectively embrace strategic planning. Carrying out the various steps in the strategic planning process is expected to facilitate the realization of organizational effectiveness. By defining a company's purpose and goals, strategic planning provides direction to the organization and enhances coordination and control of organization activities. The linkage between strategic planning and organizational performance needs analysis to get a better understanding how strategic planning is applied in practice and will improve organizational performance. Strategic planning often fails due to problems or barriers encountered at the implementation stage.

Bryson (2019) argue that strategic planning assists in providing direction so organization members know where the organization is heading to and where to expend their major efforts. It guides in defining the business the firm is in, the ends it seeks and the means it will use to accomplish those ends. The process of strategic planning shapes a company's strategy choice through the use of systematic, logical and rational approach. It reveals and clarifies future opportunities and threats and provides a framework for decision making. Strategic planning looks ahead towards desired goals. Strategic plan defines performance to be measured, while performance measurement provides feedback against the planed target (Dusenbury, 2018).

Strategic planning standardizes the processes of goal/objective setting, situation analysis, alternative consideration, implementation and evaluation that enable an organization to attain its goals and objectives (Tapinos et. al. 2015). Organizations, no matter their kinds, are established to serve specific societal needs. The success of an organization depends on its ability to direct the energies of its members in effectively serving these needs. The primary motive for the existence of any organization is often expressed in its mission and vision. It is heartwarming that most organizations (profit and non-profit alike) have mission and vision statements conspicuously displayed in their front offices. However, the efficacies of these mission and vision statements in securing the needed employees support and commitment have not being fully investigated within the Nigerian context, thus affecting overall performance.

Theoretical Review

Resource Based View Theory

The resource-based view (RBV) indicates that firm is made up of heterogeneous resources that are the sources of competitive advantage (Wernerfelt, 1984). The foundations of RBV can be found in the early studies concerning the boundaries, the distinctive competencies and the competitive advantage of the firm (Penrose 1959). Resources were defined as all the assets, capabilities, organizational processes, firm attributes, information, and knowledge of a firm (Barney 1991). However a distinction between resources and capabilities was later made by defining resources as the knowhow that can be traded (e.g., patents and licenses), financial or physical assets (e.g., property, plant and equipment), human capital, etc., while defining capabilities as the firm's capacity to deploy resources to effect a desired end (Amit & Schoemaker 1993). This distinction is further emphasized by other studies that define capabilities as the ability of firms to use their resources to generate competitive advantages (Barney 2001) and the business processes needed to configure assets in advantageous ways (O'Connor 2008).

The RBV theory has several implications for strategic management. Firstly, it suggests that firms should focus on identifying, developing, and leveraging valuable, rare, and difficult-to-imitate resources and capabilities. Secondly, it encourages firms to build and nurture a culture of innovation, learning, and continuous improvement to sustain their competitive advantage. Finally, it emphasizes the importance of aligning strategic planning and strategic objectives.

Overall, the resource-based view theory provides a comprehensive framework for understanding the sources of a firm's competitive advantage and emphasizes the role of goal setting and mission/vision in achieving organizational performance. By identifying and leveraging unique resources, firms can differentiate themselves from competitors and position themselves for long-term success in the marketplace.

Empirical Review

Akinlabi, Dogo and Asikhia (2021) explored the effect of goal setting on employees' performance of southwest universities' registry workers in Nigeria. Despite the perception that the universities in southwest Nigeria are at the fore of university education in Nigeria, there seems to be a steady decline in the performance of the universities. This has necessitated the study of the contribution of the registry workers in particular, who are the component of

workforce in the university system,

to the success of the core of university education, the performance of the registry workers in line with the increased need for more efficient processing time of key registry service delivery, and the overall need to improve the general performance of universities is drawn. A review of extant literature on goal setting and employee performance has been conducted. The study therefore recommends that universities as a way of improving employee performance must set clear, specific, measurable, attainable, and time-bound goals that are mutually set and incorporates effective feedback mechanism will serve as medium for enhancing the performance of its registry workers.

Tanui, Makokha and Nyaberi (2022) examined the effect of resource availability on organizational performance in seed processing companies in TransNzoia County. The study is guided by the Resource based theory. The study adopted a descriptive research design with a target population of 89 management staff of the seed companies. Data collection instrument was questionnaire. Piloting was done to test the validity and reliability of the data collection instruments. The data was then be analyzed using SPSS version 26 and presented through tables and graphs. The data was analyzed using descriptive statistics that is a linear regression model for the study. From the findings, resource availability ($\beta = 0.769$) was found to be positively related to organizational performance in seed processing companies in TransNzoia county, Kenya. The study recommends that the management of seed companies should ensure that regular budgeting and reviews in its strategic planning and that resource availability, outcome waste or within minimum use of resources such as energy, finances, labor and time critically in driving the success of any organization. The management of seed companies should come up with regular training programs to equip employees with latest skills, knowledge, and abilities, with the aim of building organizational capabilities and improving organizational performance. The results of the study should be relevant to the management of the seed processing companies within and without TransNzoia County.

Efi, Udofia and Imagha (2018), investigated the impact of strategic planning on organizational performance of University of Uyo, taking mission statement into consideration. Measures of organizational performance were non-financial. Population of the study was 134 principal officer staff of the university with sample size of 100 selected using Taro Yamene's formula for sample size determination. Survey research design was employed in carrying out the study. Data for the

study were generated from field survey using questionnaire to elicit information from the respondents. Data collected were analyzed using descriptive statistics. Hypotheses were tested to establish the level of influence of mission statement on performance using Linear Regression Analysis and Multiple Regression Model was used to test the overall Impact of strategic planning on performance. The result of the finding revealed that both mission statement and strategic planning have a significant influence on organizational performance of University of Uyo. We concluded that Strategic planning is vital for the overall existence, management and proper functioning of University of Uyo and other educational institutions alike. We recommended that since the available resources of University of Uyo do not conform to what the mission statement stipulates, policies on resources should be revisited, revised and better strategies for prompt sourcing, marshalling, allocation and utilization of resources should be evolved to catch up with current realities and the mission of the institution, if the University must achieve its objectives.

Bonn (2018) reviewed an empirical study on the effect of mission and vision on organizational performance in private universities in Kenya. The specific research question is how do mission and vision affect organization performance in private universities in Kenya? This was a correlational study which adopted a positivist philosophy. The study population comprised of all the 17 private universities in Kenya accredited by Commission of University Education. The unit of analysis was the board of directors, vice chancellors, heads of departments (finance, sports, human resource, research, quality assurance) and academic deans (business school) which was 136. A census technique was used in the study with frequency distributions, percentages and means for descriptive statistical analysis while correlations and regression analyses were used for inferential statistics. The study found that, mission and vision explained a significant proportion of variance in organizational performance, $R^2 = .633$. The significance value in testing the reliability of the model for the relationship between Mission and Vision on organizational performance was $F(1, 122) = 208.929$, $p = 0.00$. Therefore, the model was found to be statistically significant in predicting the relationship between the study variables. The study found that for every unit change in mission and vision, organizational performance increases by 0.867 hence implying a positive impact of mission and vision on organizational performance. Based on the findings, the study concluded that there was a significant relationship between all the independent variables and organizational performance the dependent variable. The study also concluded hat

policy and regulation positively moderated the relationship between mission and vision and organizational performance.

Gichunge (2019) examined the effect of strategy formulation on organizational performance of medium sized manufacturing enterprises in Nairobi Kenya. He investigated the effect of various administrative/legal factors on the extent to which formal strategic management are adopted, and also determined the relationship between level of competition and formal strategic management. He selected eighty medium enterprises (MEs) using simple random sampling. Primary data was collected using a semi-structured questionnaire. Results showed that strategy formulation had a significant relationship with performance of medium sized manufacturing enterprises. Further the study found out that the MEs have not fully adopted formal strategic management and that administrative/legal factors and competition influenced adoption of strategic management.

METHODOLOGY

The explanatory cross sectional survey research design was adopted for this study. The population of the study consisted of fifteen (15) insurance firms in Rivers State, Nigeria. The insurance firms consisted the population of the study. The entire population of 15 insurance firms was used as the study sample. Thus, this study is a census research which involves using the entire population rather than drawing a sample from it. The choice of census method here, is informed by the assumption that 15 is not too large to be covered. Thus, there was no need sampling at the organizational level. However, in selecting the respondents, convenience sampling was adopted and four key managers of the insurance firms (Human Resource, Operations Managers, Marketing Manager and Accounting Manager) served as the respondents. Thus, the total respondents were sixty (60) springing from the fifteen (15) insurance firms. While Spearman rank order correlation was applied for the bivariate analysis. The entire population of 15 insurance firms was used as the study sample.

Table 1: Correlation between Goal Setting and Organisational Performance of Insurance Firms in Rivers State.

Correlations

			Goal Setting	Organizational Performance
Spearman's Setting rho	Goal	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.857 **
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.000
		N	60	60
Organizational Performance	Organizational Performance	Correlation Coefficient	.857 **	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.
		N	60	60

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Source: Survey Data, 2023

The test of hypothesis presented in the above table shows a Significant level (Sig) = 0.000 which implies that (Sig<0.01) while Spearman Correlation coefficient (rho) = (0.857) also indicates that goal setting has strong and positive correlation with organizational performance. We therefore reject the Null hypotheses and accept the alternative hypotheses which state that there is a significant relationship between goal setting and organisational performance of insurance firms in Rivers State.

Table 2: Correlation between Mission/Vision and Organizational Performance of Insurance Firms in Rivers State.

Correlations

			Mission/Vision Statements	Organizational Performance
Spearman's Mission/Vision rho	Statements	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.724 **
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.000
		N	60	60
Organizational Performance	Organizational Performance	Correlation Coefficient	.724 **	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.
		N	60	60

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Source: Survey Data, 2023

The test of hypothesis two, as shown in the table 2, /the SPSS output reveals that Significant level (Sig) = 0.000 which implies that (Sig<0.01) while Spearman Correlation coefficient (rho) = (0.724)

indicates that mission/vision statement has strong and positive correlation with organizational performance. We therefore reject the null hypotheses and accept the alternative hypotheses which state that there is a significant relationship between mission/vision and organizational performance of insurance firms in Rivers State.

Discussion of Finding

Correlation.1 reveals that there is a significant relationship between goal setting and organisational performance of insurance firms in Rivers State (where $\rho = .857$ and $p = 0.000$) and based on the decision rule of $p < 0.05$ for null rejection; we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis: there is a significant relationship between goal setting and organisational performance of insurance firms in Rivers State. This result supports Pearce and Robison's (2004) findings that Corporate Planning and goal setting creates a more favorable innovation outcomes for a company

Correlation.2 reveals that there is a significant relationship between mission/vision statements and organisational performance of insurance firms in Rivers State (where $\rho = .724$ and $p = 0.000$) and based on the decision rule of $p < 0.05$ for null rejection; we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis: there is a significant relationship between mission/vision statements and organisational performance of insurance firms in Rivers State. This implies that if insurance firms develops its mission and vision effectively by involving all the stakeholders in crafting their vision and mission statements, then better organizational performance will be realized in terms of growth and expansion and revenue generation. The above findings are in agreement with the studies carried out by El-Mobayed (2006) which was conducted with 185 completed questionnaires in Palestine (in Gaza Strip) and the results showed a significant positive correlation between strategic planning and growth in sales/revenues. The study also showed a significant positive relationship between strategic planning and market share expansion. Contradictions to the above findings were studies carried out by Falshow et al., (2006), among the UK companies, they found no relationship between strategic planning and company performance. Additionally, Gibson and Cassar, (2005) found no positive relationship between strategic planning and company performance.

Conclusion

From the research findings, it can be concluded that there is a strong positive linear correlation between strategic planning and organizational performance of insurance firms in Rivers State. This study therefore concludes that goal setting and mission/vision statement significantly influences organizational performance of insurance firms in Rivers State.

Recommendation

The following specific recommendations are made based on the findings of this study:

1. Insurance firm's managers should engage in more strategic planning practices through goal setting technique in order to realize consistent improvement in performance.
2. The management should also involve all the stakeholders (top, middle and low level managers) when developing its mission and vision so that the mission statements can easily be understood by every person in the organization as this will make it easier to implement the strategic plan drawn

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